

Examining the Relationship between Work Life Balance, Job Stress and Job Satisfaction Among School Teachers : A Case of School of Pondicherry

Paper ID	IJIFR/V3/ E11/ 046	Page No.	4196-4207	Subject Area	Management- HR
KeyWords	Job Stress, Job Satisfaction , Work Life Balance, School of Pondicherry, Hafiz Hayat Campus				

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Abstract

The main purpose behind conducting the study is to investigate the relationship between work life balance, job stress and job satisfaction among School teaches. The study has been undertaken among teachers of School with reference to city of Pondicherry. A sample comprises of 171 teachers has been chosen from Govt School of Pondicherry. Random Sampling method has been used as sampling technique for the study. Questionnaire is the tool used for collecting data for the research. Data has been analyzed through Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive Statistics, Correlation and Regression analysis has been applied to draw the results of the study. The findings of the study indicate that there is insignificant relationship between job stress and job satisfaction which prove H_{10} hypothesis whereas work life balance share a moderate positive relationship with job satisfaction which are in accordance to hypothesis H_{2A} . Results of the study is helpful for educational institutions as well as teachers to get batter understating about relationship exist between job stress, work life balance and job satisfaction thus contributing toward their performance improvement.

1. INTRODUCTION

Work and Family are two important aspects of an individual's life. Changes in the workplace and employees demographic have driven the attention of many researchers toward the boundary between work and family life of employees. The main purpose behind conducting the study is to investigate the relationship of work life balance and job stress with job satisfaction among school teachers. Work life balance is an important topic of discussion in the business world. Managing work with family is an important issue as it has decisive challenges for organizations, employees and researchers. There occur a dramatic shift in the obligation of work and family life due to change in the political, social and economic values. Individuals have to deal with and acclimatize to the conflict of inter roles which has resulted from shifts in the area of work and family. (Frone & Rice, 1987). "A state where an individual manages real or potential conflict between different demands on his or her time and energy in a way that satisfies his or her needs for wellbeing and self-fulfilment is referred as work life balance" (Clutterbuck, 2003).

Satisfaction and stress both are considered to be originated from work and family lives of individuals. Globalization has altered the working environment that has led to restructuring of jobs, greater the workload demand, part time and insecurity of job. It is perceived strongly that work is an ultimate source of stress and distress among individuals. Job stress influence employee's physical as well as mental condition, it also has considerable influence on satisfaction level of employees their performance and level of absenteeism. (Tennant, 2001) Stress is the imbalance between demands perceived and resources a person have (Byrnes, 2003).

Job satisfaction is of vital importance for efficiency of an organization as well as its effectiveness. "Job satisfaction is referred to as a situation made up of any psychological, environmental and physiological combination that makes an individual trustfully says he is satisfied of his job". (Hoppock, 1935). Academic profession incorporates demands that are potentially challenging along with wide range of responsibilities. Individuals belongs to the profession experience much more problems than any other profession in maintaining their work life with personal life effectively. Job of academics produce strain as a result makes it difficult for them to meet their social, family and work obligations efficiently. Strain experienced by Academics in performing family and work role results in outcome like reducing productivity of workers, increasing absenteeism and high turnover rate among employees. The most important influence to be notice is increase in the level of dissatisfaction in academics and they complain their institutions do not corporate with them in achieving a fair balance between work and personal lives. (Fisher, 1994).

Quality of teaching at School level cannot be attained without highly satisfied teachers (Qayyum, 2013). In past few years there is tremendous increase in the number of universities in Pakistan which have increase the level of problems and pressure for academics. Organization are experiencing alternation in their working environment resulted from shifts in economic, demographic as well as social factors and academics are

not out of its influence. These changes have confronted academics to job stress which will ultimately affect their satisfaction and work life balance.

The main purpose behind conducting the study is to investigate the relationship of work life balance and job stress with job satisfaction among School teachers with reference to School of Pondicherry Hafiz Hayat Campus to get an insight into these issues.

1.1 Problem Statement

The relationship between work and family life termed as work life balance has become an important topic of discussion for current government, practitioners and academics. (Warhurst, Eikhof, & Haunschild, 2008). Issue of managing workplace needs with personal life needs is gaining importance among workers all over the world and academics of higher education institutions are not out of it. (Stanton, Noor, & Young, 2009). Teaching is a very dignified profession. The success of any nation ultimately depends upon its students and how they are getting education. It is not possible that a professors under stress, with a sense of dissatisfied with the job and having lack of balance in their work and family lives will produce good students. Lack of concern towards teacher's issues and problems is perhaps due to fewer awareness and understanding about them. The study is therefore conducting with a view to throw light on the relationship among work life balance, job stress and job satisfaction among School teacher. The knowledge about these issues will lead to creation of awareness and thus development of solution for the problems faced by School teachers.

1.2 Objectives

Fulfilment of following objectives is the main purpose behind conducting the research:

Main Objective

To find out the relationship of work life balance and job stress with job satisfaction among School teachers in Pakistan.

Sub Objectives

- ▶▶ To find out the level of work life balance, job stress and job satisfaction.
- ▶▶ To find out the relationship between job stress and job satisfaction.
- ▶▶ To find out the relationship between work life balance and job satisfaction.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Job Satisfaction

Job Satisfaction from long period of time has been an area of interest for many researchers because of its vital role in organizations effectiveness (Maslow, 1954). Job satisfaction is a concept which is versatile and complex different people perceives it differently. It's often considered in context of motivation but it's quite apart from it. It's more like a person's perspicacity, internal feeling and emotion that could be linked to things like a person feeling of achieving something (Mullins, 2005). There are two type of attitude toward the job one is positive other is negative. (Abdul, Ismail, & Jaafar, 2010). It is an established fact around the globe that a person have positive attitude toward job if he has high level of job satisfaction whereas a personal have negative attitude toward job if he is

dissatisfaction from the job. People use the term employees' attitude mostly as an interchangeable word to satisfaction of employees from their job (P.Robbins & Coulter, 2004).

B. Work Life Balance

Work-life balance is the degree to which an individual is involved in and satisfied equally with their job and personal roles (Saikia, 2011). Work life balance for individuals belongs to educational institutions are of great importance as it create knowledge for all sectors of society. Lack of balance in family and work life among academics will be harmful for all other sectors. (Greenhaus, Collins, & Shaw, 2003) According to (Veenhoven, 1991) effective balance in job and personal life makes a person more content and happier. It has been revealed in various studies that a higher desire to achieve more lead people to make extreme efforts that increase their working timing and they lost their work life balance. It ultimately reduces level of satisfaction among professional and increased the level of stress experienced by them. (Beehr & Newman, 1978). It is evident that integrating and maintain work life balance into our lives is the current need of the hour. (Mukhtar, 2012).

C. Job Stress

Stress arises when individual doubt his capability to deal with threats to their wellbeing as well as his ability to fulfill demands accurately which are being made on him (Lazarus, 1966). Conflict between employee's demands of job and degree of control employee can exert to accomplish these demands results in a harmful mental and physical response which is defined as "Workplace Stress". (Arandelović & Ilić, 2006)

Stress in the workplace is costly and keep on increasing. Causes of stress in the workplace are many that involve a complex combination of social, physical and psychological elements. Stress is difficult to measure as it influence individuals differently. Stress has a strong relationship with unhappiness as well as ill health among people. (Blaug, Kenyon, & Lekhi, 2007). Stress is not just a part of the job, a thing to be ignored or a price paid up for career success it is found to be a cause of various stress related illness either directly or indirectly. Unhealthy work environment effect employee's health both physically and mentally Many organizations seen stress as an indication of weakness and in order to avoid negative brunt kept it hidden. Stress is mostly ignored by people who are at the position to manage it. (Melanie Bickford, 2005). Sources of stress among teacher are work load, relationship with colleagues, role conflict, role ambiguity, discipline problem, time pressure, bad working condition, self-respect, inadequate support from friend, family and colleagues of low motivation among students, (Detert, Caravella, Derosia, & Duquette, 2006).

D. Relationship between Work Life balance, Job Stress and Job Satisfaction

► Nadeem & Abbas (2009) conducted a study in Pakistan to analyze the relationship between work life and job satisfaction. Data is collected from 157 employees of public and private sector through questionnaire. Data is analyzed through Correlation, Regression and Descriptive analysis. The research results indicate that job stress is negatively correlated to stress at job, family to work interfaces and job conflict. Work

overload does not influence job satisfaction. Positive relationship exists between Job autonomy and job satisfaction.

- ▶▶ Mcnall, Masuda, & Nicklin (2010) conducted the study to analyze the relationship between flexible work arrangement and job satisfaction. Data is collected from 220 employees. Data is analyzed through regression analysis. Results of the study indicate that greater the flexible work arrangements provided more will be the satisfaction employee will have from their jobs.
- ▶▶ Saif, Malik, & Awan (2011) conducted research in Pakistan to analyze relationship work life balance practices have with job satisfaction. Data is collected from 450 layoff supervisors from two large organizations in Pakistan through questionnaire. The results reveal that work life balance practices and level of job satisfaction share a Positive relationship.
- ▶▶ Rani, Kamalanabhan, & Selvarani (2011) conducted the study to evaluate the relationship between work life balance and employees satisfaction. Data is collected from 210 respondents in IT organizations through questionnaire. Multiply regression analysis was applied to drive the results. Results indicated job satisfaction have positive relationship with work life balance and negative relationship with work recognition, relationship with subordinate & supervisor and task at work.
- ▶▶ V.Varatharaj & Vasantha (2012) conducted the study to examine relationship job satisfaction have with work life balance in women. Data is collected from 250 Service Sectors working women in Chennai city through questionnaire. Data is analyzed through, Correlation, Chi-Square test, Wallis Test and Kruskals. Result shows strong positive relationship exists between job satisfaction and work life balance.
- ▶▶ Fatima & Rehman (2012) conducted research to examine role ambiguity and role conflict effect on employee's job satisfaction as well as leaving intention. Data is gathered from 120 teachers from Rawalpindi and Islamabad universities in Pakistan. SPSS and Regression Analysis are used to analyze the data. The results indicate that job role conflict and role ambiguity are negatively related to job satisfaction and positively related to job leaving intentions.
- ▶▶ Quarat-ul-ain, khattak, & Iqbal (2013) conducted the study to examine the relationship of job satisfaction with role conflict and impact of job stress on the relationship in private banking sectors employee in Pakistan. Data is collected from 350 employees through questionnaire. Data is analyzed using SPSS, Correlation and ANOVA test. Study results shows that role conflict share a positive relationship with job stress and negative relationship with job satisfaction.
- ▶▶ R.Gayathiri & Ramakrishnan (2013) conducted study to investigate the concept of quality of work life and to analyze nature of relationship it have with job satisfaction. The result indicates that the concept of work life quality is multidimensional and it influence employee's use of skills, knowledge, relationship with other and professional interaction and collaboration. Positive relationship exists between job satisfaction and quality of work.

- ▶ Yadav & Dabhade (2013) conducted research to analyze the relationship that exists between work life balance and job satisfaction of the working women. Sample is collected from education sector and banking sector. Data is collected from 150 women employees 75 women from each sector. Authenticity of data is analyzed through application of standard deviation. The results indicate that work life balance and job satisfaction share significant relationship.
- ▶ Chaudhry (2012) conducted research to analyze relationship of job satisfaction and job stress among School teachers. Gender, nature of job, experience, nature of job and sector was used as base for the study. Data is collected from six Pakistani universities three public and three private. Data is analyzed using descriptive statistics, inferential statistics, cross tabulation and frequency distributions. The results show that job stress has insignificant relationship with job satisfaction.
- ▶ Nazari & Emami (2012) conducted the research to analyze the relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction among Academics in Iran. Data was collected from 500 respondents of universities. Data is analyzed using SPSS, Correlation and Multiple Regression analysis. The results indicate that not relationship exists between job satisfaction and occupational stress.
- ▶ Usman, Akbar, & Ramzan (2013) conducted research to evaluate the effect of salary and job stress on job satisfaction of faculty. Data is collected from 100 respondents and analyzed through descriptive statistics, correlation and Regression analysis. Results reveal that no relationship exists between job satisfaction and occupational stress.

3. THE STUDY DESIGN

3.1. Hypothesis

H10 = There is no relationship between job stress and job satisfaction.

H1A = There is a relationship between Job Stress and job satisfaction.

H20 = There is no relationship between work life balance and job satisfaction.

H2A = There is a relationship between work life balance and job satisfaction.

Independent Variable - Job Stress

Dependent Variable - Job Satisfaction

Independent Variable - Work Life Balance

Causal explanation testing is the essence (Sarantakos, 2004); and (Marczyk, DeMatteo, & Festinger, 2005). Considering methodology approach this study has used survey research.

3.2 Population

Entire group of persons that conform to certain specification that are of interest to the researchers and on which results of the study can be generalized is termed as population (Polit & Hungler, 1999). All faculty members working in School of Pondicherry Hafiz Hayat Campus are Population of the study.

3.3 Sample Size

Sample is termed as portion of research population selected to make a part of the study and are envoy of the entire research population (LoBiondo-Wood & Haber, 1998). Sample of the study is constitute of 171 School teachers. Sample size is determined using (Yamane, 1973) formula:

n = Sample Size.

N = Total Population.

e = Margin of Error.

1 = Constant Number.

$n = 171.429$

$n = 171$

3.4 Sampling Design

The researcher has selected probability sampling design for the study in which simple random sampling is used. Researchers preferred simple random sample over the others because it provides the assurance that sample will accurately reflect the population on the basis of criteria used for simple random sampling (Cooper & Emory, 1995) (Johnson & Christensen, 2010).

3.5 Measures

Questionnaire has been used as data collection tool for the study. Questionnaire is a good quantitative research tool for analyzing attitudes and behavior of humans. (Francis, et al., 2004). The questionnaire is composed of four parts. The first section deals with job stress measured with an 8 item scaled Questionnaire proposed by (Ning, 2004, Verret, 2012). Each item is measured on five point Likert Scale. Ranges from strongly agree at 1 to strongly disagree at 5. The second section deals with job satisfaction measured with a 14 item scaled questionnaire proposed by (Mukhtar, 2012). Each item in the scale is measured by five point Likert Scale. Ranges from strongly agree at 1 to strongly disagree at 5. The third section deals with work life balance measured with a 14 item scaled questionnaire proposed by (Hayman, 2005). Each item is measured by seven point scale ranges from not at all at 1 to all the time at 7. The fourth part of questionnaire constitute demographic information age, gender, marital status and experience are included in this section.

3.6 Procedures

Data has been analyzed through Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive Statistics, Correlation and Regression analysis has been applied to draw the results of the study

4. RESULTS

The respondents in the study 43% were Male and 57% were Female. The majority of the respondents in the study were married (53%) and 47% of the respondents reported themselves as unmarried. All the respondents in the study ranged in age from 21 years to 50 years. 68% of the respondents were between the ranges of 21 to 30 years, 25% of the

respondents were between the range of 31 to 40 years and 7% of the respondents were between the ranges of 41 to 50 years. 25% of the respondents in the study have less than 1 year of experience in the School, 32 % of the respondents have experience between the ranges of 1 to 3 years, and 43% of the respondents have experience of more than 3 years.

Table I: Descriptive Statistics

Characteristics	Percent (%)
Gender	
Male	43.4
Female	56.6
Marital Status	
Married	52.6
Unmarried	47.4
Age	
21-30	68.4
31-40	25.0
41-50	6.6
Experience	
Less than 1 year	25.0
1 to 3 years	31.6
more than 3 years	43.4

Table II: Correlations

1. Job Stress		(.627)	
2. Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.052	(.850)
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.658	
3. Work Life Balance	Pearson Correlation	.326**	(.638)
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.004	
Values of Cronbach Alpha are given in Parenthesis.			
** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Results in Table II indicate that Cronbach Alpha for Job Stress, Work Life Balance and Job Satisfaction were .627, .638 & .850 respectively.

Based on the given statistics H10 is not rejected. The results show that there is insignificant relationship between job stress and job satisfaction.

Based on the given statistics hypothesis H2A is supported. The results show that a significant and positive correlation exists between work life balance and job satisfaction. The correlation is moderate in strength.

Results in Table III indicate that Job Stress and Work Life Balance together explain 10.7% of the variation in the Job Satisfaction ($R^2 = .107$). ($F=4.358$, $p= 0.016$). An inspection of individual predictors reveal that Work Life Balance ($B=.216$, $p=.005$) is positively correlated with Job Satisfaction suggest that high level of Work Life Balance is

associated with high level of Job Satisfaction. Occupational Stress ($p = .974$) is not a predictor of Job Satisfaction.

Table III: Regression Analysis

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	R Square	F	Sig	B	T value	Sig	Hypothesis
Job Stress	Job Satisfaction	.107	4.358	.016	.013	.067	.947	H10 Is Accepted
Work Life Balance					.216	2.915	.005	H2A Is Accepted

6. CONCLUSION

The research contributes in existing body of knowledge by investigating the relationship of Work Life Balance and Job Stress with Job Satisfaction among School Teachers. The findings of the study confirm both hypotheses. Relationship between Job Stress and Job Satisfaction are found insignificant among School Teachers which are in accordance to the findings of (Nazari & Emami, 2012, Usman, Akbar, & Ramzan, 2013, Qayyum, 2013). Relationship between work life balance and job satisfaction is found significant and of moderate positive nature which mean increase in Work Life Balance will result in increase in Job Satisfaction which are in accordance to the findings of (Nadeem & Abbas, 2009, Saif, Malik, & Awan, 2011, V.Varatharaj & Vasantha, 2012). Thus none of the two hypotheses is rejected.

7. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study is of significance for the academics, researchers and organizations. The study contributes to existing body of knowledge by providing an insight into relationship exist between work life balances, job stress and job satisfaction among School teachers. Globalization has brought tremendous changes in working conditions thus give rise to various issues and problems for employees. The study will help to get awareness about the issues and problems faced by employees at work place that will be of beneficial for organizations and institutions to formulate strategies that will booster satisfaction level, minimize job stress and maintain a healthy work life balance among employees thus ultimately enhance organizations effectiveness and efficiency. The study is also of importance for researchers as it provides a first step initiative for further studies.

8. LIMITATIONS

The present study suffered from some limitations that must be known before taking into consideration the results of the research. The main limitation of the study is as participant of the study is from a particular School the area of investigation is limited. Due to this factor results of the study cannot be generalized to large population.

9. REFERENCES

- [1] Saikia, Dr. Jatindra Nath, (December 2011). A study of the Work Life Balance among the Academics of Higher Education Institutions: A Case Study of Golaghat District, Assam. Retrieved January Thursday, 2014
- [2] Abdul, M., Ismail, H., & Jaafar, N. I. (2010, October). Job Satisfaction Among Executives: Case of Japanese Electrical And Electronic Manufacturing Companies, Malaysia. 6(2), 165-173.
- [3] Anxo, D., Boulin, J. Y., Fagan, C., Cebrián, I., Keuzenkamp, S., Klammer, U., . . . Toharía, L. (2006). Working time options over the life course: New work patterns and company strategies. Centre for European Labour Market Studies HB (CELMs HB), Gothenburg, Ireland.
- [4] M., & Ilić, I. (2006). Stress in Workplace - Possible Prevention *Facta Universitatis*, 13(3), 139-144.
- [5] Bassegy, M. (1995). *Creating Education Through Research: A Global Perspective of Educational Research for the 21st Century*. Kirklington Moor Press.
- [6] Beehr, T. A., & Newman, J. E. (1978, December). Job Stress, Employee Health, and Organizational Effectiveness: A Facet Analysis, Model, and Literature Review. *Personnel Psychology*, 31(4), 665-699.
- [7] Blaug, R., Kenyon, A., & Lekhi, R. (2007). *Stress at Work*. The Work Foundation's Principal Partners, London.
- [8] Byrnes, R. (2003). *Unwind: 10 Ways to Manage Stress and Improve Your Wellbeing*.
- [9] Chaudhry, A. Q. (2012, June). The Relationship between Occupational Stress and Job Satisfaction: The Case of Pakistani Universities. *International Education Studies*,
- [10] Clutterbuck, D. (2003). *Managing Work-life Balance: A Guide for HR in Achieving Organisational and Individual Change*. London: Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development.
- [11] Cooper, D. R., & Emory, C. W. (1995). *Business Research Methods*. by Richard d Irwin.
- [12] N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (2000). *Handbook of Qualitative Research*.
- [13] Detert, R. A., Caravella, T., Derosia, C., & Duquette, R. D. (2006). Reducing stress and enhancing the general well-being of teachers using T'ai Chi Chih® movements: A pilot study. *Californian Journal of Health*, 4(1), 162-173.
- [14] Fatima, G., & Rehman, W. u. (2012). Impact of Role (Ambiguity and Conflict) on Teaching Assistants' Satisfaction and Intention to Leave: Pakistani HEIs. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 7(16).
- [15] Fatima, N., & Sahibzada, D. S. (2012, April 30). An Empirical Analysis of Factors Affecting Work Life Balance among School Teachers: the case of Pakistan. *Journal of International Academic Research*, 12(1).
- [16] Fisher, S. (1994). *Stress in Academic Life : the mental assembly line*. Buckingham [England]: Buckingham [England] ; Bristol, PA, USA : Society for Research into Higher Education : Open School Press, 1994.
- [17] Francis, J. J., Eccles, M., Johnston, M., Walker, A., Grimshaw, J., Foy, R., . . . Bonetti, D. (2004). *Constructing Questionnaires Based On The Theory Of Planned Behaviour A Manual For Health Services Researchers*. School Of Newcastle, Centre For Health Services Research. United Kingdom: Centre For Health Services Research.
- [18] Frone, M. R., & Rice, R. W. (1987, January). Work-Family conflict: The effect of job and family involvement. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 8(1), 45-53.
- [19] Gall, M. D., Gall, J. P., & Borg, W. R. (2003). *Educational Research: An Introduction*.
- [20] Greenhaus, J. H., Collins, K. M., & Shaw, J. D. (2003). The relation between work-family balance and quality of life. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 63, 510-531.
- [21] Hayman, J. (2005, July). Psychometric Assessment of an Instrument Designed to Measure Work Life Balance. *Research and Practice in Human Resource Management*, 13(1), 85-91.
- [22] Hoppock, R. (1935). *Job Satisfaction*. New York and London :: Harper and brothers.

- [23] Johnson, B., & Christensen, L. (2010). Educational Research: Quantitative, Qualitative and Mixed Approaches. (4 ed.). SAGE.
- [24] Lazarus, R. S. (1966). Psychological Stress and the Coping Process. McGraw-Hill.
- [25] LoBiondo-Wood, G., & Haber, J. (1998). Nursing Research: Methods, Critical Appraisal, and Utilization. (4th, Ed.) Mosby.
- [26] Marczyk, G., DeMatteo, D., & Festinger, D. (2005). Essentials of Research Design and Methodology. New Jersey, Canada: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- [27] Maslow, A. H. (1954). Motivation and personality (1st ed.).
- [28] Mcnall, L. A., Masuda, A. D., & Nicklin, J. M. (2010). Flexible Work Arrangements, Job Satisfaction, and Turnover Intentions: The Mediating Role of Work-to-Family Enrichment. *The Journal of Psychology*, 144(1), 61-81.
- [29] Melanie Bickford. (2005). Stress in the Workplace: A General Overview of the Causes, the Effects, and the Solutions. Canadian Mental Health Association, Newfoundland and Labrador Division.
- [30] Mukhtar, F. (2012). Work life balance and job satisfaction among faculty at Iowa State School.
- [31] L. (2005). Management & Organisational Behaviour (7th ed.). Prentice Hall / Pearson Education.
- [32] Myers, M. D. (2009). Qualitative Research in Business & Management. SAGE.
- [33] Nadeem, M. S., & Abbas, D. Q. (2009, May). The Impact of Work Life Conflict on Job Satisfaction of Employees in Pakistan. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 4(5), 63-83.
- [34] Nazari, K., & Emami, M. (2012). The Investigation Of The Relation Between Job Stress And Job Satisfaction (Case Study In Faculty Members Of Recognized Public And Private Universities In The Province Of Kermanshah). *Advances in Natural and Applied Sciences*, 6(2), 219-229.
- [35] Ning, T. (2004). Antecedents And Consequences Of Role Stress In Hospitality Industry. National School Of Singapore, Department Of Management And Organization, Singapore.
- [36] Onwuegbuzie, A. J., & Leech, N. L. (2005, June). Taking the "Q" Out of Research: Teaching Research Methodology Courses Without the Divide Between Quantitative and Qualitative Paradigms. *International Journal of Methodology*, 39(3), 267-295.
- [37] P. Robbins, S., & Coulter, M. (2004). Management (8th ed.). Prentice Hall.
- [38] Polit, D. F., & Hungler, B. P. (1999). Nursing Research: Principles and Method (6 ed.). Lippincott.
- [39] Qayyum, c. (2013, June). Job Satisfaction of School Teachers across the Demographics (A Case of Pakistani Universities). *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 35(1), 1-15. Retrieved from www.bia.ca.
- [40] Quarat-ul-ain, khattak, M. A., & Iqbal, N. (2013, April). Impact of Role Conflict on Job Satisfaction, Mediating Role of Job Stress in Private Banking Sector. *Interdisciplinary Journal Of Contemporary Research In Business*, 4(12), 711-722.
- [41] R. Gayathiri, & Ramakrishnan, D. L. (2013, January). Quality of Work Life – Linkage with Job Satisfaction and Performance. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 2(1), 01-08.
- [42] Rani, S., Kamalanabhan, & Selvarani. (2011). Work / Life Balance Reflections On Employee Satisfaction. *Serbian Journal of Management*, 6(1), 85-96.
- [43] Saif, D. M., Malik, M. I., & Awan, M. Z. (2011, September). Employee Work Satisfaction and Work - Life Balance: A Pakistani Perspective. *Interdisciplinary Journal Of Contemporary Research In Business*, 3(5), 606-617. Sarantakos, S. (2004). Social Research.
- [44] Stanton, P. M., Noor, K. M., & Young, S. H. (2009). Work-life Balance and Job Satisfaction : A study among Academics in Malaysian Higher Education Institutions. 14th Asia Pacific Management Conference (APMC): Enhancing Sustainability in the Asia Pacific: Entrepreneurship and Innovation (pp. 1-15). Surabaya, Indonesia: Airlangga School.

- [45] Tennant, C. (2001). Work-related stress and depressive disorders. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research*, 697-704.
- [46] Tuli, F. (2010, September). The Basis of Distinction Between Qualitative and Quantitative Research in Social Science: Reflection on Ontological, Epistemological and Methodological Perspectives. *Ethiop. J. Educ. & Sc.*, 6(1), 97-108.
- [47] Usman, S., Akbar, M. T., & Ramzan, D. M. (2013, (September - October)). Effect of Salary and Stress on Job Satisfaction of Teachers in District Sialkot, Pakistan. *IOSR Journal Of Humanities And Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 15(2), 68-74.
- [48] V.Varatharaj, & Vasantha, S. (2012, March). Work Life Balances A Source Of Job Satisfaction - An Exploratory Study On The View Of Women Employees In The Service Sector. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(3), 450-458.
- [49] Veenhoven, R. (1991, March 28). Is Happiness Relative? 1-34.
- [50] Verret, L. B. (2012). Factors Affecting School Stem Faculty Job Satisfaction.
- [51] Warhurst, C., Eikhof, D. R., & Haunschild, A. (2008). *Work less, live more? : critical analysis of the work-life boundary / edited by Chris Warhurst, Doris Ruth Eikhof and Axel Haunschild*. Basingstoke ; New York : Palgrave Macmillan, 2008.
- [52] Yadav, R. K., & Dabhade, N. (2013). Work Life Balance And Job Satisfaction Among The Working Women Of Banking And Education Sector – A Comparative Study. *International Journal of Advancement in Education and Social Sciences*, 1(2), 17-30.
- [53] Yamane, T. (1973). *Introduction to Statistic (3rd ed.)*. Longman.

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